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WYMAGANIA DOTYCZĄCE KSZTAŁCENIA ZAWODOWEGO NAUCZYCIELI W UNIWERSYTETACH WIELKIEJ BRYTANII

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Streszczenie. Aby przeanalizować przygotowanie zawodowe nauczycieli w uniwersytetach Wielkiej Brytanii, należy wziąć pod uwagę cechy kadry nauczycielskiej uczelni, wymagania dotyczące edukacji i badań brytyjskich nauczycieli, funkcje pracy profesora, podkreślić zestaw cech osobistych i zawodowych nauczyciela zgodnie ze standardami zawodowymi. Stwierdzono, że wymagania dotyczące poziomu wykształcenia i stopnia naukowego nauczyciela uczelni są uzależnione od przedmiotu nauczania oraz rodzaju instytucji edukacyjnej, w której nauczyciel pracuje. Podkreśla się, że ciągły rozwój zawodowy, którego celem jest doskonalenie procesu nauczania i uczenia się, pozostaje ważny dla nauczycieli szkół wyższych. Badanie zagranicznych doświadczeń w kształceniu zawodowym nauczycieli pozytywnie wpłynie na poprawę krajowego systemu kształcenia przyszłych nauczycieli.

Słowa kluczowe: wyższa edukacja, instytucja nauczania wyższego, kształcenie nauczycieli, stanowisko naukowe, stopień doktora filozofii, kryteria zajmowania stanowisk naukowych, standardy zawodowe.

REQUIREMENTS FOR PROFESSIONAL TEACHER TRAINING IN UNIVERSITIES OF GREAT BRITAIN

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Abstract. To analyze the professional training of teachers in British universities, it is important to consider the features of the teaching staff of higher education institutions, requirements for education and research of British teachers, the peculiarities of the professor, to highlight a set of personal and professional characteristics of teachers in accordance with professional standards. It was found that the requirements for the level of education and degree of a teacher of a higher education institution depend on the subject being taught and the type of educational institution in which the teacher works. It is emphasized that continuous professional development remains important for teachers of higher educational institution, which aims to improve the process of teaching and learning. It is noted that the study of foreign experience of professional training of teachers will have a positive impact on improving the Ukrainian system of teaching future teachers.

Key words. higher education, higher educational institution, teacher training, academic ranks, Ph.D. degree, academic promotion criteria, professional standards.

ВИМОГИ ДО ПРОФЕСІЙНОЇ ПІДГОТОВКИ ВИКЛАДАЧА В УНІВЕРСИТЕТАХ ВЕЛИКОЇ БРИТАНІЇ

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Анотація. Для аналізу професійної підготовки викладача в університетах Великої Британії важливо розглянути особливості професорсько-викладацького складу закладу вищої освіти, вимоги щодо освіти та наукової діяльності британських викладачів, особливості роботи професора, висвітлити комплекс особистісних і професійних характеристик викладача відповідно до професійних стандартів. З'ясовано, що вимоги до рівня освіти та наукового ступеню викладача закладу вищої освіти залежать від предмету, який викладається, та від типу навчального закладу, в якому працює викладач. Підкреслюється, що для викладачів ЗВО важливим залишається постійний професійний розвиток, який має за мету вдосконалення процесу навчання та викладання. Зазначено, що вивчення закордонного досвіду професійної підготовки педагогів матиме позитивний вплив на вдосконалення вітчизняної системи навчання майбутніх викладачів.

Ключові слова: вища освіта, заклад вищої освіти, підготовка викладача, академічна посада, ступінь доктора філософії, критерії обіймання академічних посад, професійні стандарти.

Introduction. All universities in Great Britain are legally independent corporate institutions. The Department for Education and Skills is responsible for all universities in England. In Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland universities come under the respective devolved governments. Before 1992 there was a distinction between polytechnics and universities, but as a result of the 1992 Further and Higher Education Act, Great Britain has a unified system with 113 university institutions.

Academic ranks in Great Britain are the titles, relative importance and power of employees in universities. In general the country has three academic career pathways: one focused on research, one on teaching, and one that combines the two. In general they are divided into:

- professor;
- reader;
- senior lecturer, senior teaching fellow, principal lecturer;
- lecturer, teaching fellow;
- assistant lecturer, demonstrator, seminar leader, associate lecturer, graduate teaching assistant;
- visiting professor.

The titles of Honorary Professor, Honorary Professor of Practice, Honorary Senior Lecturer and Honorary Lecturer are awarded to recognise and reward an agreed contribution to the teaching and/or research of the University, or input through professional standing, in the interests of the University (*Department for Education (n.d.) Teachers' Standards 2020*).

It is difficult to get a permanent position in the university of Great Britain. About half of the positions available are given on the basis of fixed-terms contracts. For this reason, mobility within the system is quite high. At the same time, promotion can be dependent on the change of an institution or on being able to negotiate a higher scale at your own institution against an external offer. However, while it is true that many academic positions in Great Britain are temporary, the ratio of permanent positions is considered to be low when compared with the high level of permanent positions in a European context. At the same time, the very fact that relatively junior members of academic staff can get permanent lectureships soon after acquiring their PhDs is something that is unique for the Great Britain academia.

From Lecturer level most university positions are permanent. There is normally a probation period of three years for all permanent positions, after which the position is permanent but not tenured.

A Ph.D. degree is normally required for obtaining a lectureship. Postdoctoral training of at least one year is generally an advantage for applying for a Lecturer position, but not a requirement. More recently, there is a tendency of doing 3-5 years of postdocs before young scholars are able to obtain a position of a Lecturer or some other permanent position. However, it is also possible to be appointed Lecturer after the Ph.D. degree.

The step between A and B lecturer is a salary step and you can be appointed Lecturer B directly if your qualifications meet the standards required for this pay scale (defined by individual institutions/departments).

Once appointed a permanent Lecturer position there are three ways to be promoted:

- 1) by applying for a vacant position;
- 2) being nominated for promotion by heads of department;
- 3) applying for promotion under the internal career advancement system with the institution.

Promotions are assessed and granted by an academic committee set up by the individual institution. Applying for promotion is the normal way to climb the career ladder. This can be done within one's own institution but it is important to note that mobility between UK institutions is high and promotion is thus often obtained when applying for a higher position in another institution.

The requirements for promotion are experience in teaching and research. Professorships are normally not awarded unless you have published at least two books. Particularly important is the Research Excellence Framework (REF) which has increased the importance of research productivity in assessing faculty performance. Besides quality of work, promotions depend largely on the financial constraints of the institution.

All academic appointments involve requests for references, which are supposed to advocate rather than critically evaluate the applicant. A reference from a well known senior scholar is often an important part of the appointment process.

On overall, the system is very reactive since, if one position vacates, which is often due to great inter-university mobility, a new position opens almost immediately to cover for the vacated position. The successful candidate is usually the one who fits the particular need of the department at that particular point in time.

Let's examine requirements for the position of senior lecture on the example of University of Warwick. All requirements are divided into the following criteria:

Research and Scholarship criteria

- Demonstrably knowledgeable about key concepts and developments in a given discipline (subject area expertise)
- Clearly capable of undertaking research/evidence based inquiry in their area of expertise (discipline or pedagogy) which demonstrates impact on practice/policy and/or can make an original contribution to knowledge either in research or teaching
- Demonstrated ability to undertake and disseminate or publish original, high quality, research which makes a significant contribution to the discipline or to pedagogy.
- Has achieved national eminence and authority for the quality and impact of their research and scholarship and is developing an international profile
- Building an international reputation, influencing the field, through the distinction of their research and publication, which might include significant contribution to impact for the major development of one or more fields of knowledge
- Has an international reputation for research and scholarship, demonstrating subject leadership through the encouragement of research among members of staff and suitably qualified students.
- Has achieved and sustained, outstanding and widely recognised international eminence and authority in their subject through the distinction of their research, publications and leadership.

Teaching and Learning criteria

- Able to deliver routine teaching to a satisfactory standard
- Able to develop and deliver teaching to a standard evidencing good practice at Foundation, UG or PG Level with evidence of enhancement and engagement with national frameworks and standards
- Able to design, deliver, evaluate and assess teaching to a good standard, to engage effectively with students and collaborate with colleagues to inform the enhancement of own and others' teaching practices.
- Able to design, deliver, evaluate and assess teaching to a high standard, engage effectively with students and collaborate with colleagues to inform the enhancement of own and others' teaching practices.
- Demonstrates leadership in relation to enhancement of teaching or the engagement of students, the development of educational practice of colleagues, local policy and/or guidance development, or change in educational practice.
- Demonstrates leadership in learning and teaching which is of a national standard impacting positively on a wide range of learners
- Sustained leadership through the enhancement of teaching or the engagement of students, the development of educational achievement by other academics, external educational policy development, and/or societal change.

Impact, Outreach, Engagement criteria

- Building a reputation for academic contributions in specialist area

- Recognised externally for work in specialist field
 - Developing a reputation and recognition with key stakeholders for the broader value of specialist activity
 - Developing regional/national recognition for work demonstrating value of broad based academic activity.
 - An established regional or national reputation, which might include significant contribution to impact for the major development of one or more fields of knowledge at an international level
 - Developing an international reputation for impact, outreach or engagement, which demonstrates the broader external value of academic activity.
- Collegiality, Leadership, Management criteria*
- Able satisfactorily to plan and organise own academic activity.
 - Able satisfactorily to contribute across a variety of administrative roles relating to academic activity.
 - Demonstrate the ability actively to organise and manage activity in support of academic processes, showing emerging leadership ability within immediate group.
 - Track-record of management capability within the Department. Demonstrates leadership ability within a wider group or department.
 - Effective management and development of academic activities important to income and/or reputation within or beyond the University.
 - Leadership which may be within the University or within a discipline or related academic activity (*Teaching profile preparation, 2002*).

SEDA is the professional association for staff and educational developers in Great Britain, promoting innovation and good practice in higher education (*SEDA. Professional Development Framework. Values or principles, 2020*).

The association's objects are:

- to support individuals in their professional activities and development aspirations;
- to recognise individual professional achievements;
- to advance professional practice;
- to enhance the experience of students participating in higher education;
- to encourage the development of learning communities with shared values.

Award recipients will have shown how their work is informed by the SEDA Values:

- developing understanding of how people learn;
- practicing in ways that are scholarly, professional and ethical;
- working with and developing learning communities;
- valuing diversity and promoting inclusivity;
- continually reflecting on practice to develop ourselves, others and processes.

A set of standards is proposed for university teaching. Embedding these within the Higher Education Academy UK Professional Standards Framework (UKPSF) would allow a more robust assessment of whether a university teacher has met a minimum acceptable threshold.

A teacher's primary responsibility is to facilitate learning. In our view, an excellent teacher is someone who does their utmost to ensure that every student reaches his or her potential. In England the current criteria is laid out in the Department for Education's Teachers' Standards. These represent a demanding set of standards which Initial Teacher Training students and Newly Qualified Teachers (NQTs) are assessed against, the latter in their first year of teaching while on probation.

So what changes when school students enter university and encounter a greater variety of styles of university teaching, a greater number of university teachers and, more importantly, university teachers with a wider range of attributes and aptitudes for teaching?

University teaching over the last 30 years or so has changed enormously, as has teaching in schools. This is roughly the length of time one of us has been in Higher Education and the other in secondary schools and Higher Education. The changes and improvements in university teaching have not been uniform, in contrast to the changes that have happened in schools during this period. But one aspect that has changed in Higher Education is the increased importance placed on high quality and effective teaching (and by implication the quality of learning) by all stakeholders: students, universities and government. National Student Satisfaction surveys and higher tuition fees clearly have a bearing on this too.

The usual requirement is that new lecturers or new teaching staff undergo a three-year induction/probation period. During this time there will be varying amounts of staff-development training available, mentoring from within their own discipline/department by a member of academic teaching staff, and the requirement to pass a postgraduate certificate or similar qualification equivalent to a certain number of credits at Level 7 within the National Qualifications Framework.

By the very nature of such a certificate being a Level 7 qualification within a national framework that can sit alongside Masters' level programmes, this can look much more like an academic qualification as opposed to an assessment suitable for establishing that a trainee teacher has met an agreed set of standards and qualified to teach. There is likely to be some kind of assessed project on an aspect of teaching, learning or supporting students, and possibly related to staff development workshops. There will also be a 'practice' element in teaching and learning involving peer observations of teaching and discussions with a mentor, again assessed in written form by a reflective portfolio.

The overarching framework within Great Britain is the Professional Standards Framework (UKPSF) developed by the Higher Education Academy (HEA) (*Taylor S. 2016*). As its first aim, the UKPSF 'supports the initial and continuing professional development of staff engaged in teaching and supporting learning'. The Academy supports the Framework by providing a recognition and accreditation service which enables staff providing teaching and/or learning support to be recognised, depending on their role and experience as either Associate Fellow, Fellow, Senior Fellow and Principal Fellow of the Academy based on a set of statements outlining the key characteristics of someone performing in four broad categories of typical teaching and learning support roles within higher education. The professional development activities described earlier for probationary members of staff would be expected to enable someone passing probation to meet the criteria for the designation of Fellow.

The following eight (draft) standards are based on the published Teachers' Standards, and in every case there is a strong argument as to why a university teacher (who is, after all, training), should be assessed against each and every one of these within their own discipline and carried out by an appropriately qualified 'professional tutor'.

A university teacher is expected to demonstrate, through the collection of evidence, that the quality of their teaching facilitates learning to enable all students to reach their potential.

To achieve a satisfactory standard a university teacher is required to:

1. Set high expectations which inspire, motivate and challenge;
2. Promote good progress and outcomes by;
3. Demonstrate good subject knowledge;
4. Plan and deliver well-structured teaching sessions;
5. Adapt teaching to respond to the strengths and needs of all students;
6. Make accurate and productive use of assessment;
7. Manage behaviour effectively to ensure a good and safe learning environment;
8. Fulfil wider professional responsibilities.

Conclusion. The structure of scientific knowledge and academic positions in higher education institutions of Great Britain is analyzed. It is established that the requirements for the level of education and scientific degree of a teacher depend on the subject being taught and on the type of educational institution in which the teacher works. It has been found that professional standards are documents that set requirements for knowledge, skills, abilities, competencies, experience, values, personal qualities, etc., which are necessary for the performance of certain professional duties. Universities in Great Britain offer higher education teacher training programs based on professional standards developed by either the Academy of Higher Education or the Association for the Professional and Educational Development of the Faculty. The proposed results should be integrated with values and practices.

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